

Imtiaz Dharker, *Luck Is the Hook*, (Northumberland: Bloodaxe Books Ltd., 2018), Price: Rs. 969.00, Pages: 127.

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This book under review is the sixth collection of poetry published by Imtiaz Dharker in 2018 by Bloodaxe Books. *Luck is the Hook* is a huge surreal canvas where the author has literally painted with her heart to produce poetry on a myriad of themes ranging from longing for love, to a haunting; from historical to cultural and from personal grief to universal wisdom. The title of the collection is a pure reflection of Dharker's precision and creative inclination for rhyme and rhythm in the creative process, converting simple words into poetry and poetry into painting.

Imtiaz Dharker was born in Lahore, Pakistan and her family shifted to Glasgow, Scotland when she was just a few months old. Though she has lived in many countries, and has been exposed to various cultures, (she even calls herself a '*cultural mongrel*') she denies to be labelled under any kind of compartments. The phenomenon of dislocation and displacement thus finds a vivid treatment at her hands in her various poems.

This collection also commences with a series of poems, wherein Chaudhri Sher Mobarik attempts to pronounce the proper Glaswegian words like '*loch*' and '*hen*'. It is remarkable how an outsider proudly subscribes to the language and code of conduct of the country where he/she has migrated. The act of incorporating the tonal and behavioural changes has not been carried out to show or prove anything to the natives of the particular country to which he/she has migrated, but it is more like proving to one's own self of how one has been able to adopt and adapt, adeptly to the culture of the host country. In all her poems, the idea of journeying and travelling has always been an embellishment of an essential essence that is just hers. Here also, the idea of travelling has not

just been limited to the physical and actual travelling. But here the poems talk about what the process of travelling does to one; mentally as well as emotionally. Travelling as a process is an act of moving forward but paradoxically, it also takes one backward, into the past, down the memory lane. So, it is a kind of time travelling into the past when one is physically in the present and probably moving forward but mentally and emotionally, one seems to be moving backward.

There is also a beautiful portrayal of how our lives are fangled up between two extremes of what we want and what is wanted from us; between what we think and what society wants us to think; and between our silent rebellion and our brutal obedience. Our actions and our behaviour always revolve around the thought of “*log kya kahengey!*” (What will people say!). Out of the sheer fear of what people will say, we end up always, busy playing a role, which is in reality is very much different from our actual selves and what we actually want to do.

‘...and the answer to why
Was always log kya kahengey,
The beginning and the end,
What will people say.’ (Fankle, p. 16)

Poems in the like ‘*Arc*’, ‘*A Haunting*’, and others create an eerie effect on the readers. The existence of several well known haunted places in the Asian regions probably inspired her to create poems which can render a surreal, ghostly experience to the readers. The poems go on to describe incidents when the dead are trying to overcome the gulf between the inanimate and the living world by contacting and falling in love with living beings. Dharker’s previous collection titled “*Over the Moon*”, published in 2014 also dealt with the death of her husband and the loss. Here the same sense of haunting has been extended, even to the extent of haunting of the memories of a loved one who has sadly, passed away. Poems are written in a particular sense of time and space. Here the idea of space gets metaphysical connotations, because loss of someone has been accredited with even the loss of emotional space that was shared with the departed person. She has likened it to the creation of a void in space *sans* (without) warmth.

The phenomena of haunting has also been extended to the haunting of words. She writes,

‘...words are nothing
but gravestones unless they haunt
you day and night...’
(A haunting of words, p. 53)

For Imtiaz Dharker, poetry is all about using the most accurate and the most precise words for conveying what she wants to convey and her words paint a canvas that one can visualise and appreciate. With the use of certain words in poetry, she propels the readers to think about several matters that otherwise, go unnoticed and she raises a pertinent voice over issues which are generally wrapped in silences. Her quest of searching for the right word for her poems is evident from the following lines,

‘...words are the pearl.
Dive for them and we become real.’
(Arc, p. 33)

The current collection of poems is brimming with both historical and political contexts. She was commissioned to write poems on the history of St. Paul’s cathedral when it was bombed during the World War II in the year 1940. With her words she has given a creative edge to an otherwise simple historic event. While describing the incident she writes,

‘...Like a giant boar, pig-ugly, it tore
Out of the sky with its load
Of death....’
(Unexploded, p. 82)

In all the poems pertaining to historic events, she bears the capacity to create a visual image in our minds. Though St. Paul’s cathedral escaped any major damage, miraculously, the readers of her poem can easily experience the horror and gravity of the fateful day’s events. by. The incident when the altar of the church was ruined and when the statues of the cherubs were damaged, is described as follows, later they will recall it.

Like something suspended in time,
Like first love at the last frost fair.
They will say. That was the day. I was there
(The Elephant is walking on the River Thames, p. 62).

Imtiaz Dharker is a versatile artist who is not only a poet but also a painter and a documentary filmmaker. Her versatility and her connection with art are depicted in all her poems, which she has composed in response to the solo exhibitions of several South Asian artists. Her poem thread is in response to Neha Choksi’s multi-channel film installation, which revolved around the idea of an individual and how the formation of one’s individuality is the outcome of one’s own surroundings and one’s own community. Another poem written by Dharker is based on the postcard size paintings of an artist named Risham Sayed.

She has made postcard size paintings of Lahore city which is transforming day in and day out as an advent of innovation and construction taking place in the flick of an eye. Dharker captured the theme and conveyed the idea that post-cards and photographs cannot capture the true essence of the city, which is long gone. With the changes taking place in the city, we tend to lose a sense of belonging towards a particular place, which is always evolving and changing. The other artists whose exhibitions have been a source of inspiration for her poetry are that of Mehreen Murtaza, Hetain Patel and Waqas Khan.

Intiaz Dharker has beautifully dealt with the issue of technology creeping in, into the very fabric of our lives and how it (technology) has brought us closer to each other, close enough to track people from our mobile phones even when they are flying in the air. But the poems in this collection force us to ponder over a compelling question of whether technology is really bringing us closer to people or is it actually taking us away and making us indifferent towards our surroundings. In her humorous poem titled *The Garden Gnomes*, the verses of which are on mobile phones, she has used comedy and a humorous yet subtle tone by writing the following lines,

‘...The gnomes are busy
Watching Games of Thrones,
Jamming buttons on controllers,
Checking their likes on mobile phones....’
(The Garden Gnomes are on their mobile phones, p. 107)

The most poignant characteristic of this collection are the sketches sketched by her. The poems written by her are amplified by her sketches. Dharker has used a black ink pen and a handmade paper for her sketches, which render a unique texture to her drawings. Here, words and descriptions create a brilliant visual image in front of our minds which, at times is in stark contrast with the sketches drawn by her. The sketches do not correspond to one particular poem but at times they all come together and illustrate major themes and concerns handled by her.

Luck is the Hook is a collection, which can leave any reader awestruck with the number of themes that are dealt with by the poet. The image of the hook lingers in the reader’s mind throughout the collection, which shows the dichotomous nature of the hook. When luck is considered as the hook, then it may either bring two things together to bind them or it can even tear two fused things apart.